

A CLINICAL SINGLE CASE STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFECT OF VAJIGANDHADYA TAIL MATRA BASTI ALONG WITH SHAMAN CHIKITSA IN GRUDHRASI W.S.R. TO SCIATICA

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Shaman Chikitsa, Sciatica.

ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda eighty Vataja Nanatmaj Vyadhis are described, Grudhrasi is one of them in which there is pain starting from spik and then radiating to posterior aspect of jangha, janu, pad along with stambh, todwat pain and spandan. It can be correletd with Sciatica in which pain radiating along with sciatic nerve pathway up to foot. In Ayurveda Basti karma one of the procedure of Panchkarma is described as a best treatment for Vatavyadhi. This study aim to evaluate the efficacy of Vajigandhadya Tail Matra Basti which is mentioned in Yogratnakar for treatment of Grudhrasi along with Shaman chikitsa. It is single case study. A 55 yr old female patient was dignosed with Grudhrasi and was treated with Vajigadhadya Tail Matra basti along with Shaman chikitsa. Symptomatic assessment was carried out after 8 days. Satisfactory outcome was observed and quality of life of patient was improved.

KEYWORDS: Grudhrasi, Vajigandhadya Tail Matra Basti,

1. INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda Acharya Charaka described 80 types of Vataja Nanatmaj Vyadhi which are mainly caused due to vitiation of Vata Dosha, Grudhrasi is one of them in which the patient has the gait of Grudhra (Vulture) (गृध्रवत् चलते यस्मिन्). In Grudhrasi vitiated Vata Dosh hamper the Ghrudhrasi Nadi (sciatic nerve) causing pain in posterior aspect of Sphik (waist), kati (lower back), uru (hip), prusth (back), janu (knee), jangha (calf region), paad (foot) with sthambha (stiffness), ruk (pain) toda (pricking pain) spandan (tingling sensation).

In kaphanubandhata Tandra (drowsiness), gaurav (heaviness), arochak (anorexia) will be present.^[1]

Grudhrasi can be correled with sciatica as resembles the cardinal symptoms.

In sciatica pain that radiates along with the pathway of sciatic nerve due to sciatic nerve root pathology that makes difficulty to walk and having pain and paresthesia along sciatic nerve distribution posterior aspect of thigh up to foot. The main cause is herniation or degenerative changes of intervertebral disc. Other causes are spinal stenosis, spondylolisthesis, osteoarthritis trauma, tumors, cysts, prolonged sitting, improper posture.^[2]

The annual incidence of sciatica is estimated about 1% -5%. Sciatica can occur at any age more common between 3rd to 5th decade. Lifetime prevalence of sciatica estimates ranging from 13% to 40% according to International Journal of community medicine and Public health.^[3]

Basti is the main treatment of Vatavyadhi as described in Ayurved. And Grudhrasi is one of the nanatmaj Vata vyadhi treated with Basti chikitsa. After detailed examination and assessment the patient was diagnosed as Grudhrasi. The patient was given Vajigandhadya Tail Matra basti with Yograj guggul, Kaishor Guggulu, Sutshekhar Ras and Rasnasaptak Kwath as Shaman chikitsa which has significant relief in lower back pain, stiffness, tingling sensation and also improvement in gait.

2.1. METHODOLOGY

This is a single clinical case study conducted in Radhakisan Tosniwal Ayurved Rugnalaya and Anusandhan Kendra Akola. The patient was treated with *Shodhan* and *Shaman chikitsa* along with diet and lifestyle modification, counseling to see the efficacy of *Shodhan* with

Vajigandhadya Tail Matra Basti with *Shaman Chikitsa* for 7 days. Improvement was assessed. After proper explanation about treatment regimen written consent was taken before treatment.

2.2. CASE HISTORY

A 60 year old female patient came to *Kayachikitsa* OPD of Radhakisan Tosniwal Ayurved Rughalaya and Anusandhan Kendra Akola with complaints of low back pain radiating to right lower limb with stiffness in lower back and posterior aspect of right lower limb since last one year. For that she was taking analgesics and anti-inflammatory medications from local practitioner but having temporary symptomatic relief so she came to *Kayachikitsa* OPD of R T Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Akola and admitted for further Ayurvedic management.

2.2.1 Chief Complaints

The onset of symptoms starts from one year ago. She gradually developed low back pain radiating to posterior aspect of thigh, knee, and calf region up to foot of right lower limb. Also experienced tingling sensation in right lower limb. Later on she experienced walking difficulty unable to walk 100 meters since last 2-3 months.

2.2.2 Associated Complaints

Constipation

Disturbed sleep due to pain

2.2.3 H/O Past illness

She has no any traumatic history also no any prior surgical history.

2.2.4 Family History

Not significant

2.2.5 Personnel History

Appetite: Good, Diet: Non Vegetarian, Addiction: No any addiction, Sleep: Disturbed, Bowel: constipation, Micturition: Regular

2.3 Clinical Findings

Physical Examination

Astavidh Pariksha and general examination

<i>Astavidh Pariksha</i>	General Examination
<i>Nadi</i> (pulse)-82/min <i>Vata kaphaja</i>	Pulse-82/min
<i>Mala</i> (bowel) – <i>malavstamba</i>	BP-130/80mmHg
<i>Mutra</i> (micturition) – <i>samyak</i>	RR-18/min
<i>Jivha</i> (tongue) – <i>niram</i>	Temperature-98.4 F
<i>Shabda</i> (speech)- <i>Prakrut</i>	RS-AEBE, No wheez crepts
<i>Sparsh</i> (skin)- <i>Anushnashit</i>	CVS-S1S2 Normal
<i>Druk</i> (eyes)- <i>Prakut</i>	CNS-Conscious oriented
<i>Akruti</i> (posture)- <i>Madhyam</i>	P/A-soft L/S-Not palpable

Locomotor Examination

Inspection	1. Antalgic gait 2. Difficulty while walking and sitting for long duration. 3. Restriction of spinal and hip movements.
Palpation	1. Good muscle tone 2. Muscle power of both lower limbs-5/5
Range of movements(ROM)	1. Forward flexion of the lumbar spine is limited to 30cm above ground 2. Left lateral flexion is limited to 30 ⁰ with pain. 3. Right lateral flexion is limited with 30 ⁰ with pain. 4. Extension is limited to 10 ⁰ with pain.
Straight leg raised test(SLR)^[4]	1. Positive for right lower limb at 70 ⁰ 2. Negative for left lower limb.
Bragards test^[5]	1. Positive for right lower limb. 2. Negative for left lower limb.
Slum test^[6]	1. Positive for right lower limb. 2. Negative for left lower limb.

Dignosis: Vataj Grudhrasi.

2.4 Assasment Criteria

The assessment criteria for subjective criteria are as follows.

Sr.no.	Symptoms	Criteria	Gradation
1.	<i>Ruk</i> (pain in the lower lumbar region radiating to right lower limb) VAS score(0-10)	No pain(0) Mild pain(VAS score 1-3) Moderate pain(VAS score 4-6) Severe pain(VAS score 7-10)	0 1 2 3
2.	<i>Stambha</i> (Stiffness)	No stiffness Stiffness for few minutes after sitting long duration Stiffness for more than 1 hour or more once in a day but not affecting daily routine work	0 1 2

		Stiffness for 1 hour or more but affecting daily routine work	3
3.	<i>Sakasta Chakraman</i> (Pain while walking)	No pain Pain while walking more than 1 kilometer Pain while walking more than 0.5 kilometer Pain while walking more than 0.25 kilometer	0 1 2 3
4.	<i>Toda</i> (prickling sensation)	No prickling sensation Mild prickling sensation Moderate prickling sensation Severe prickling sensation	0 1 2 3
5.	<i>Spandana</i> (Throbbing)	No throbbing Mild throbbing for few minutes daily Moderate throbbing for many times a day not affecting daily routine work Severe throbbing affecting daily routine work.	0 1 2 3

3. Therapeutic intervention

1. *Snehan* with *Til Tail* and *Nadi swedan* over *kati* and *dway pad* for 7 days.
2. *Matra Basti* with *Vajigandhadya Tail* for 7 days
3. *Shaman Chikitsa* with – *Yograj Guggul* 1 tab (250mg) thrice a day
Kaishor Guggul 1 tab (250mg) thrice a day
Sutshekhar Ras 1 tab (250mg) thrice a day
Rasnasaptak Kwath 20 ml twice a day.

Pathya apathya (diet and lifestyle regimen)

Ingredients of *Vajigandhadya Tail Basti*

1. *Ashwagandha*
2. *Bala*
3. *Bilva*
4. *Dashmool*
5. *Eranda Tail*(castor oil)

Tail is prepared according to the guidelines.

Dose and duration of study of *Vajigandhadya tail Matra Basti* is 60 ml daily for 7 days.

4. Follow up and outcome: The patient has considerable decrease in low back pain, stiffness and pain in posterior aspect of right lower limb. Her gait also improved well and spine range of movement also improved. The subjective and objective criteria before and after treatment was evaluated (assessment criteria)

Detail of assessment criteria

Subjective parameters

Sr.no.	Assessment Parameters	Before Treatment	After Treatment
1	<i>Ruk</i> (pain in the lower lumbar region radiating to right lower limb) VAS score(0-10)	2	1
2	<i>Stambha</i> (Stiffness)	3	1
3	<i>Sakasta Chakraman</i> (Pain while walking)	3	0
4	<i>Toda</i> (prickling sensation)	3	1
5	<i>Spandana</i> (Throbbing)	3	1

Objective parameters

1	ROM of lumbar spine		
	1.Forward flexion	30cm above ground	20 cm above ground
	2.Right lateral flexion	30 ⁰ with pain	10 ⁰ without pain
	3.Left lateral flexion	30 ⁰ with pain	10 ⁰ without pain
	4.Extension	10 ⁰ with pain	20 ⁰ without pain
2	SLR test		
	1.Right lower limb	Positive	Negative
	2.Left lower limb	Negative	Negative
3	Bragards test		
	1.Right lower limb	Positive	Negative
	2.Left lower limb	Negative	Negative
4.	Slum test		
	1.Right lower limb	Positive	Negative
	2.Left lower limb	Negative	Negative
5.	Gait	Antalgic Gait	No Antalgic gait

5. DISCUSSION

In this single case study the patient was suffering from pain at lower lumbar region which was radiating to the posterior aspect of thigh, knee, calf region up to foot with stiffness also had altered gait diagnosed as *Grudhrasi* (Sciatica).The patient was treated with Ayurvedic intervention including *Shodhan chikitsa* with *Vajigandhadya Tail Matra basti* and *Shaman chikitsa* with *Yograj Guggul*, *Kaishor Guggul*, *Sutshekhhar Ras* and *Rasnasaptak kwath*. The patient get significant relief in her symptoms.

Basti is one of the most important therapy among the five procedures of *Panchkarma*. According to *Acharya Charak* *Basti* is half of the treatment and many other *Acharyas* called it is complete treatment.

Basti is main procedure for management of *Vata Vyadhi*. According to *Ayurveda* the main *Sthan* of *Vata* in our body is *Pakwashay*. And in *Basti* procedure, drug introduced in *Pakwashay* which is then enter in *Grahani*. *Pakwashay* is site of *Purishdhara kala* and *Grahani* is site of *Pittadhara kala*. According to *Acharya Dalhana* *Purishdhara kala* and *Asthidhara kala* are same and *Pittadhara kala* and *Majjadhara kala* are same.^[7] So from this evidence it is clear that *Basti* has direct action on *Asthi* and *Majja Dhatu*.

Vajigandhadya Tail^[8] is recommended for treatment of *Grudhrasi* as suggested by *Acharya Yogratnakar* which contains *Ashwagandha*, *Bala*, *Bilva*, *Dashmool* and *Erand Tail* has *Vatahara* and *Brihana* properties help to alleviate *Ruk*, *Stambha* and *Toda* in *Grudhrasi* and also nourish and improve the health of nerves, muscle and joints.

Yograj Guggulu^[9] mainly having properties like *tikta*, *kashaya*, *katu rasa* and *ushna*, *ruksha guna*, *ushna virya* acts as *VataKapha shaman*, *ama pachan* and *agni deepan* properties. The main target area of drug is *asthi majjagat vata*.^[5]

Kaishor Guggulu^[10] mainly having properties like *tikta kashaya rasa* and *laghu*, *ruksha guna*, *Ushna virya* and *madhur vipaka* acts as *vedana sthapana*, *strotoshodhan*, *deepan pachan* properties.^[6]

Sutshekhar Ras^[11] mainly contains *kajjali*, *suvarn*, *vatsnabh*, *chaturjat tankan* having properties like *ushna virya*, *katu tikta kashay madhur rasa*, *laghu ruksha tikshna vyavayi guna madhur katu vipaka* act as *Vata Pitta shamak yogvahi*, *rasayan*, *vatvahinya shamak*, *vedanashamak*.^[8]

Rasnasaptak kwath^[12] contains *rasna*, *guduchi*, *aargwadh*, *devdaru*, *gokshur*, *erand*, *punarnava* having properties like *vatashamak*.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study *Vajigandhadya Tail Matra Basti* along with *Shaman chikitsa* provided significant relief in *Grudhrasi* (*Sciatica*).

1. There is marked improvement in pain in lower lumber region which was radiating to posterior aspect of thigh, knee, calf region up to feet of right lower limb
2. Improvement in *Stambh*, Stiffness and Tingling sensation.
3. Marked improvement in gait which became normal.

This result highlights the effect of *Vajigandhadya Tail Matra Basti* with *Shaman chikitsa* in the management of *Grudhrasi*. However further studies with large sample size and for longer duration are needed to verify standard outcome.

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